

QUIZ**LAST NAME: AUDU****FIRST NAME: SUNDAY****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: SIX****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2019 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- English language usage and mechanics in academic writing are critical for communicating with other researchers in a credible manner. The American and Standard British English are both variants of world English. Which of the following statements are true regarding "World English?"**
 - American English is superior to SBE.
 - Most divergence is not associated with national histories and cultural development.
 - They are more similar than different, especially with the "educated or scientific" English.¹**
 - Some words differ in pronunciation but not spelling.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK: PERIOD 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 27.

2. **Understanding the kinds of sources readers expect in academic writing.**

- A source that analyzes published primary data is called tertiary and used for evidence.
- Read the primary source for evidence, while secondary learn from others and tertiary for overviews of the subject.²**
- A primary source is the only reliable source.
- A secondary source includes general encyclopedias and dictionaries.

3. **Plagiarism.**

- Ideas, theories, and facts used in a paper with a signal to the source constitute plagiarism.
- Completed work with a list of sources consulted but not cited in work is an example of plagiarism.
- A piece of information that is common knowledge and available from numerous sources if not cited constitute plagiarism.
- Is when a writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of the source.³**

4. **Choice of research design is directly tied to the research problem and purpose. What constitutes a qualitative research approach?**

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 24–25.

³ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 5.

- Qualitative research is suited to promote a deep understanding of a social setting or activity as viewed from the perspective of the research participants.**⁴
- Qualitative research is suited to promote a deep understanding of a social setting or activity as viewed from the perspective of the researcher.
- Qualitative research is suited to promote a deep understanding of a social setting or activity as viewed from the perspective of the research participants and the researcher.
- Qualitative research is suited to promote a deep understanding of a social setting or activity as viewed from the perspective of the researcher.

5. **Qualitative research approaches include one of the following categories.**

- Case study, ethnography, phenomenology, grounded theory, and narrative research.
- All qualitative research approach is based on constructivist.
- Case study, ethnography, phenomenology, grounded theory, and narrative research.
- Case study, ethnography, phenomenology, grounded theory, narrative research, and hermeneutics.**⁵
- Constructivist theory is a genre of inquiry in qualitative research.

6. **Citation management software.**

⁴ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 7–14.

⁵ Bloomberg and Volpe, 10–12.

- Citation management software is limited in style.
- Citation management software allows an author to organize, store, and retrieve information, such as citations for books, articles, and Websites.⁶**
- A citation management software allows multiple styles in a paper.
- A citation management software can create a complete bibliography or reference list according to the desired style.

7. **Style guides in academic writing.**

- A style guide is all about the correct usage of punctuations, grammar, and vocabulary.
- A style guide is for beginners in academic writing.
- Ensure consistency in approach to a writing style.⁷**
- Style guide eliminates creativity in writing.

8. **Ethical presentation of data in academic writing. Use of graphs and charts.**

- Graphs can also mislead when the image encourages readers to misjudge values.
- Graphs can also mislead by implying false correlations.
- It should not distort its data or its relationships to make a point.
- All are true in communicating data ethically in research.⁸**

⁶ Turabian, 89.

⁷ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 24.

⁸ Turabian, 63.

9. **Bibliographic entries for in-text citations.**

- The critical parameter for the identification of a source used is the year of publication and page numbers.
- The critical parameter for the identification of a source used is the page numbers.
- The critical parameter for the identification of a source used is the Author's name and year of publication.⁹**
- The critical parameter for the identification of a source used is the publisher.

10. **Data analysis in qualitative study research.**

- Qualitative data analysis is complex requires patience and reflection to make sense of multiple data.
- Qualitative data summarized in a credible manner to reflect the participants' perceptions, opinions, and ideas.
- Qualitative data analysis about bringing order, structure, and meaning to the information collected.
- All the statements are true in qualitative data analysis.¹⁰**

⁹ Turabian, 128.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, 95–99.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
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